

SCREENING BACTERIAL STRAINS OF *BACILLUS* GENERATION BY PROTEASE ACTIVITY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14023184>

Abstract. Today, medicines account for more than 15% of the total volume of all microbial biotechnology products produced in the world. Enzymes occupy a special place among medicinal substances. For example, proteolytic enzymes are often used in the treatment of digestive diseases. These enzymes are also widely used in the treatment of various wounds, burns, in order to remove tissues that have undergone necrosis. Lipases are also used in case of digestive disorders. Proteases with fibrinolytic activity are effectively used to dissolve blood clots. The enzymes streptokinase and urokinase are used to restore the function of the heart, lungs, and blood vessels of the arms and legs.

Keywords: proteases, *Bacillus*, enzyme, proteolytic, producer, amino acids, glucose, fructose, culture, strain

Object: *Bacillus subtilis* bacterial strains, protease enzyme, protein content.

The subject: screening of proteolytic enzyme products, selection of the active product of the protease, enzyme separation, purification and determination of the physicochemical property.

Introduction. In modern microbiology and biotechnology, proteolytic enzymes are among the main enzymes used in various manufacturing industries, and the scientific function of biological catalysis is evidence of the widespread use of enzymes. Microbial protease enzymes have been widely used in enzymatic processing of protein-preserving raw materials, including milk protein, skin augmentation, and are one of the promising sources for obtaining products such as free amine nitrogen, amino acids, and glucose-fructose derivatives. Also, globally, the enzyme protease, which is synthesized in microorganisms, is widely used not only in the food industry, but also in the pharmaceutical, medical fields [1].

From hydrolytic enzymes in the literature, despite the fact that the protease enzyme is less illuminated compared to other enzymes, the products of this enzyme are *Bacillus* sp., *Bacillus polymyxa*, *B. subtilis*, *B. amyloliquefaciens*, *B. mutant strain licheniformis*, *Bacillus flavothermus*, *B. megaterium*, it has been studied to be a stearothermophilis strain. But, in the manufacturing industry, to obtain protease preparations from microorganisms, more bacteria of the *Bacillus* generation, including *B. amyloliquefaciens*, *B. licheniformis*, is used as *megaterium* [7].

Protease is a class of peptide-hydrolase enzymes that hydrolyze proteins, composed of peptides and other compounds, structured from peptide bonds [4,8]. In recent times, most scientists are focusing on microbial proteases, and these enzymes are widely used in the pharmaceutical, food, skin industries, as well as in the production of protein hydrolyzates and in many other branches of the national economy.

The first microbial protease crystal form was obtained in Karlsberg Laboratory in 1974 by Langom and Otetsonom from bacterial strains of *Bacillus* generation. Individual authors divide proteases into four classes: serine-conserved protease (KF 3.4.21.), Cysteine-conserved protease

(KF 3.4.22), asparagine-conserved protease (KF 3.4.23), and metal-conserved protease (KF 3.4.24) [5].

Bacteria of the *Bacillus* generation have polyphermal activity. Their enzyme system consists of a set of enzymes belonging to different classes. *Bacillus* mainly produce hydrolases. These microorganisms synthesize chitinase, α -amylase, protease, cellulase and a number of other enzymes [6]

In a meat-peptone soup, it forms a cotton-like precipitate, while a thin layer of the liquid surface is characteristic. They are chemoorganoheterotrophs, ammonifying proteins, breaking down starch and glycogens [2,3].

Material and methods. The resulting bacterial cultures were grown by planting agaric pepton in a nutrient medium in special test tubes, and periodic replanting was carried out in new pots, maintained at a temperature of 4°C.

In our isolated strains, screening was conducted on protease enzyme activity. A liquid nutrient medium has been selected for active bacterial strain screening (g/l): NaCl – 5, MgSO₄ – 0.5, Na₂HCO₃ – 0.1, pepton-10, baseline pH environment indicator 6.0.

Bacteria were grown in standard flasks with a volume of 250 ml in a 50 ml feed medium, 150 rpm, 50°C and 72 h in a rotary vibrator.

The *Bacillus subtilis*-5 strain, selected to increase the biosynthetic process, was grown in two stages: 1) Nutrient medium (g/l) for inoculation from producer: NaCl – 5, MgSO₄ – 0.5, Na₂HCO₃ – 0.1, pepton – 1, initial pH environment 6.0.

Bacterial strains were grown in flasks with a volume of 250 ml in a 50 ml feed medium, 150 rpm, 50 °C and 3 hours in a rotary vibrator, and the inoculate content for the fermenting feed medium is 0.3 %.

2) Selected liquid nutrient medium for fermentation (g/l): corn flour – 30, corn starch – 20, yeast extract – 5, (NH₄)₂HPO₄ - 10, KCL – 0.015, MgSO₄ – 0.005, CaCL₂ – 0.001, pH environment 6.0.

Bacteria were grown in flasks with a volume of 250 ml in a 50 ml feed medium, 150 rpm, 50°C and 72 hours in a rotary vibrator.

To distinguish highly active products from the hydrolysis of casein, 1% of well-clayed starch was placed in the petri saucer. The periphery of the bacterial colony forms a colorless zone according to kleister hydrolysis. When an iodine solution is dripped into the Petri Cup, the nutrient medium is dyed blue.

The following nutrient media were also used to study the physiological-morphological characteristics of the isolated and selected strain:

Peptone agar: pepton-10.0, sucrose-1.0, NaCl-0.5, KH₂PO₄-0.5, MgSO₄ - 0.5, drinking water-1000 ml.

Main part. To study the cultural properties and quality indicators of bacterial isolates of the selected *Bacillus* generation, the colony shape, color, hydrolysis zone size by starch, colony color, surface appearance and other parameters of bacterial isolates were studied. Proteolytic properties have been screened for isolates of *Bacillus* progeny being studied in a 1% casein solid GPA nutrient medium, the following strains that differ in Colony color uniform leakage, milky color, transparent color, and hydrolysis zones – *Bacillus sp* with hydrolysis zone 4.1 mm.-2.3.6 mm *Bacillus sp* -4.4.8 mm *Bacillus sp* -5, and 4.2 mm *Bacillus sp*.-7 bacterial cultures were selected for further research.

At the next stage, from isolates with a high hydrolysis zone, *Bacillus sp.* -5 and *Bacillus sp.* Screening was conducted on protease activity in -7 isolates. Screening results in active *Bacillus sp.* -5 isolate has a protease content of 8.2 one./ml, protein content of 1.2 mg/ml, hydrolysis zone of 4.8, and α -amylase activity of 2.4-one./ ml. *Bacillus sp.* In the -7 isolate, these pointers have a protease activity of 6.4 one./ml, protein content is 1.4 mg/ml, hydrolysis zone is 4.2, and α -amylase activity is 1.8-one/ml (Table 1).

As can be seen from the table, the fact that the isolates *Bacillus sp* – 5 and *Bacillus sp* – 7 are active, in which the protease activities are 8.2 and 6.4 one./ ml, while the smooth-amylase activities are 2.4 and 1.8 one./ ml.

Thus, the *Bacillus sp* – 5 isolate on protease activity is listed from the BIM collection subtilis-184 was found to be even more active than the strain and was selected for further research.

Table 1.

Protease of bacterial isolates of Bacillus generation and a screening on the amylase-amylase activities

№	Strain	Separated source	Protease activity, one./ ml	α -amylase activity, one./ ml
1	Bacillus sr. – 2	Bukhara region wheat field	3,8±0,2	0,6±0,06
2	Bacillus sr. – 4	Surkhandarya region wheat field	4,5±0,25	0,8±0,08
3	Bacillus sr. – 5	Bukhara region wheat field	<u>8,2±0,4</u>	<u>2,4±0,2</u>
4	Bacillus sr. – 7	Bukhara region wheat field	<u>6,4±0,2</u>	<u>1,8±0,04</u>
5	Bacillus cereus – 151	Industrial waste of Uzbekistan	3,7±0,4	1,5±0,1
6	Bacillus subtilis – 184	BMK	<u>5,8±1,6</u>	<u>5,6±0,3</u>
7	Bacillus licheniformis – 84	Sulphurous Earth soil, Uzbekistan	4,6±0,2	1,4±0,1
8	Bacillus megaterium – 86	Sulphurous Earth soil, Uzbekistan	0,8±0,4	0,7±0,2

Note: control clock BMK-whole union micro-organism collection; figures drawn under are reliably distinguished from varint.

In our study, bacterial isolates were used, isolated from samples from wheat fields of Bukhara and Surkhandarya regions. Bacterial strains from the *Bacillus* generation develop rapidly, mainly in peptolous nutrient media, in different types of mineral and starchy nutrient muxites. Therefore, the growth and development of such microorganisms depend not only on the pH environment or temperature, but also on the composition and amount of various salts contained in the nutrient mucite. Protein biosynthesis allows to select the optimal conditions for growing and slightly increase the biosynthetic abilities of bacterial cells.

Conclusion. It was thought about such parameters as the selection of active proteolytic enzyme products from strains of the *Bacillus* generation and the optimal conditions of enzyme formation, methods of obtaining the enzyme *Bacillus subtilis* -5 protease and determining its physico-chemical properties, obtaining an active enzyme preparation.

In the dynamics of growth and development of the *Bacillus subtilis* -5 strain, the influence of external factors, conditions of biosynthesis have been studied. At the same time, the optimal nutrient environment selected for this strain has been modified and the optimal pH, temperature dependence are given.

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